
REDSHIFT AS A 4-DIMENSIONAL GEOMETRIC PHENOMENON: A STATIC HYPERSPHERE COSMOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

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Jozsef Koncz*^{1,2}

¹Independent researcher

²BSc in Software Engineering
University of Tokaj, Hungary

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ABSTRACT

This study proposes an alternative explanation for galactic redshift within a higher-dimensional geometric framework. The model posits that our three-dimensional world is embedded in a four-dimensional hypersphere, and that redshift arises from the wave propagation of light in 4-dimensional space rather than from the expansion of space. The approach conceptually aligns with Einstein's static universe idea [Einstein, 1917] but recasts it within a novel multi-dimensional geometric setting that avoids the paradoxes of the standard expanding model. Furthermore, the model offers a natural interpretation for dark matter and dark energy phenomena by deriving them from interactions between the 3-dimensional and 4-dimensional spaces.

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Foreword

This study deals with theoretical physics. The author does not claim that this is the only possible explanation for the phenomena discussed, and those who are inspired by the contents of this study to conduct further research to empirically prove its findings will undoubtedly refine and elaborate on its statements.

The study will discuss the possible causes of redshift, taking into account what we know and what we do not know about space and time, considering the theoretical possibility of the existence of more than three dimensions of space, and seeking evidence for this.

1 Basics

In 1929, Edwin Hubble published his famous article [Hubble, 1929] in which he stated that the recession velocity of galaxies (measured by redshift) is proportional to their distance. This finding later became known as Hubble's law, and it was the first experimental evidence that the universe is expanding. However, Hubble also sought an answer to the question of what causes this phenomenon, and out of caution, he referred to the velocity of galaxies as "apparent radial velocities." [Hubble, 1929, 168. o.] Hubble did not want to assume that galaxies were physically moving in space (like a car leaving an observer), but rather suggested that space itself was expanding. Although the cosmological model has evolved considerably since then, there are still areas that are not, or are not sufficiently, explained, such as the question

*kuetuo@student.unithe.hu; j.koncz.official@gmail.com

of "dark matter" or "dark energy," or the data obtained from counting galaxies, which are unexpected based on today's cosmological model.

The basic observation, which can be empirically verified, can therefore be described by the following simple model:

U = the boundary of the visible universe

E = the position of an observer on Earth

G1, G2 = the position of a given galaxy and its apparent radial vector as indicated by the redshift

G3 = a galaxy located at the edge of the visible universe, whose radial vector shows a recession close to the speed of light

Figure 1: Observed redshift

From this approach, it could be concluded that the Big Bang occurred near point "E," but this is not supported by any other observations, so we will exclude this possibility from further investigation. Instead, let us project the observation onto the situation of how an observer at point "G3" would see the motion of the marked galaxies.

U = the boundary of the visible universe

G3 = the position of an observer in a G3 galaxy

E = our galaxy (and planet Earth) located at the edge of the universe visible from the G3 galaxy, of which radial vector shows a recession speed close to the speed of light relative to the G3 galaxy

G1, G2 = the position of a given galaxy and its apparent radial vector as indicated by the redshift. In this case, the vectors were not determined based on observations, but rather by interpolating the redshift model based on Earth-based observations, as schematically depicted in Figure I-a to point G3.

Figure 2: Redshift interpolated to the point G3

To better understand the situation, let us now superimpose the model based on ground-based observations and its interpolation to point G3.

U = the boundary of the visible universe

Let us observe the anomalies:

G1 = It is obvious that the two vectors cancel each other out.

G2 = The sum of the two vectors implies a displacement that would contradict the observations.

Figure 3: Superposition of observed and interpolated redshift data

Hubble introduced the theory of an expanding space to resolve the issue, noting that galaxies do not actually move, but rather space expands.

The theory of an expanding universe raised a number of concerns and paradoxes, which led to debates that shaped the development of cosmology. Hubble's 1929 observations [Hubble, 1929], that the recession of galaxies is proportional to their distance would have placed Earth at the center of the universe, which contradicted the Copernican principle. Interestingly, this theory had already been mathematically derived two years earlier, in 1927, by Georges Lemaître [Lemaître, 1927], who also raised the possibility of the expansion of the universe and the "primordial atom" (or "initial singularity," possibly the Big Bang singularity). The paradox of the apparent central position was finally resolved by the assumption that space expands uniformly at every point. The question of distances exceeding the speed of light raised relativistic concern [Peebles, 1993], but it turned out that the expansion of space itself does not violate Einstein's theory of relativity. Einstein himself doubted the compatibility of the conservation of matter and the expansion of space [Einstein and de Sitter, 1932], which was later explained by the redshift and the decrease in energy density. The discovery of the acceleration of expansion in 1998 [Riess et al., 1998] brought further mysteries, as the nature of dark energy remains unknown to this day [Carroll, 2001]. Lemaître's work [Lemaître, 1927] was particularly important in providing a theoretical basis for later observations, although it was initially less recognized. On a philosophical level, questions arose as to why the parameters of expansion are favorable to life (anthropic principle) [Barrow and Tipler, 1986], and what exists beyond the boundaries of the observable universe. These questions remain open. In other words, while the theory of an expanding universe has solved many questions, it has also raised new ones to which we still have no answers.

Is there another explanation for the redshift of galaxies? How can Einstein's original theory of a static universe and Hubble's idea that galaxies do not actually move be reconciled with the redshift?

2 New foundations

Let us start again with the redshift observed by Hubble (and others) and Einstein's theory of a static universe [Einstein, 1917]. Remember that Hubble claimed that the redshift of galaxies is an apparent velocity.

Before we proceed, it is very important to recognize and accept that there are two fundamental concepts that we do not understand thoroughly enough. These two concepts, or physical phenomena, are light and time. Light exhibits both wave and particle characteristics [Manning and al., 2015, Jacques et al., 2007]. Defining time is even more complicated as the table below summarizes:

Table 1: Different Physical Approaches to the Concept of Time

APPROACH	CONCEPT OF TIME	CHARACTERISTIC SOURCES
Newtonian	Absolute, uniform flow flow	Principia Mathematica (1687)
Thermodynamic	Direction of entropy increase	Boltzmann theory (19th century)
Special relativity	Observer-dependent, dilating dimension	Einstein (1905), Hafele-Keating experiment
General relativity	Part of the curvature of space-time	Einstein (1915), GPS technology
Quantum gravity	May be discrete or an illusion	Rovelli, Loop Quantum Gravity (21st century)

All this is important because the redshift observed by Hubble is actually based on these two principles. The nature of light and time, which is a tool for analyzing light as a phenomenon.

If we accept that we do not know enough about the nature of light and time, or all aspects of them, we can start from new foundations to understand what might cause the redshift observed by Hubble.

3 Spatial dimensions

Our known world consists of three spatial dimensions. According to certain theories, there may be more dimensions than this, in various forms. To understand why it is difficult to think in terms of multidimensional space, let's take a step back and think in two-dimensional space. This is useful because the 2D world is easier to understand, and we have words for it in everyday language. For example, a 2D circle can become a sphere in the 3D world, but we have no everyday words to describe what it might be in the 4D world², and our imagination cannot comprehend it either, since we have no visual 4D experiences and cannot have any. However, the relationship between the 2D and 3D worlds models the relationship between the 3D and 4D worlds well, as we will prove later.

An observer living in a 2D space (represented by the stick figure) encounters different shapes and phenomena in his world. Let's imagine it, perhaps the illustration will help. He knows the line, the circle, the square. He sees light. He knows colours, you could say he lives in a 2D world. He is an enlightened person, because he knows that his world is flat, but infinite forward and backward, right and left.

Figure 4: 2D world

First, let's see how the observer sees his own 2D world. More precisely, how we think he sees it. In fact, only we see it this way he never does. Moreover, we only see it this way from a 90° angle; if we looked at it from a different angle, it would appear distorted, or from a 0° angle, for example, it would not be visible at all, because 2D space has no thickness.

²In fact, there are artificial terms such as hypersphere and hypercube (or tesseract), but these are not widely known, and mentioning them does not evoke any visual associations in most people, unlike mentioning a circle, sphere, or cube.

Now let's talk about whether the 2D world is flat. Because there is no doubt that people living in a 2D world see their world as flat from the inside.

Figure 5: 2D world – perspective

So let's look at it from a perspective view. This view helps us understand how the 2D world, which is part of a larger 3D world, can be positioned within.

Now let's see what a 2D world would look like if it were positioned in a 3D world as a curved space, similar to the surface of a cylinder.

Figure 6: 2D world – curved space

An observer living in a 2D space would not notice anything about the curvature of his world. Although we would see his world as distorted, he would not perceive this at all. He could only know the true shape of his world from effects that come from the 3D world and have some effect on the 2D world.

So how could the 2D world discover that it is located in a 3D world? Only if they interact with each other. For example, if there were a phenomenon originating in a 2D world that spread to the 3D world and had an effect on the 2D world again, it would be perceptible there. This phenomenon would cause anomalies that could not be explained by the physical laws that apply in the 2D world.

3.1 The interrelation of spatial dimensions

At this point, it is very important to clarify the relationship between 2D and 3D spaces. One popular assumption is that 3D space is created from a finite or infinite number of 2D spaces, so to speak, layered on top of each other. This can be easily refuted using mathematical methods. The basis for the refutation is that the thickness of 2D space $d(2D)$ is exactly 0. We can write 3D space as the product of the numbers v (vertical), h (horizontal), and d (depth), with the restrictions that ³

$$v > 0 \wedge h > 0 \wedge d > 0$$

At the same time, 2D space can never be interpolated into 3D space, because no matter how many layers we calculate, as long as $v^{(2D)}$ and $h^{(2D)}$ can be interpreted on the set of real numbers greater than 0, their product cannot:

$$v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \neq v^{(2D)} \cdot h^{(2D)} \cdot ([\text{number of layers}] \cdot d^{(3D)})$$

because

$$v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \neq v^{(2D)} \cdot h^{(2D)} \cdot (\mathbb{R}_{>0} \cdot 0)$$

$$v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \neq v^{(2D)} \cdot h^{(2D)} \cdot 0$$

$$v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \neq 0$$

In other words, while it can be part of a 3D space, i.e. one or more 2D spaces can be located in it as independent objects, it is not the 2D space objects that make up 3D space. The existence of 3D space is independent of the existence of one or more 2D spaces located within it.

³ \wedge = the logical AND operator

The above equation can also be written for 4D spaces. In this case, the fourth spatial dimension is denoted by the letter w . The constraint is similar:

$$v^{(4D)} > 0 \wedge h^{(4D)} > 0 \wedge d^{(4D)} > 0 \wedge w^{(4D)} > 0$$

Let's write this down in a formula, keeping in mind that the value of w is always exactly zero in 3D space, similarly to the value of d in 2D space:

$$v^{(4D)} \cdot h^{(4D)} \cdot d^{(4D)} \cdot w^{(4D)} \neq v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \cdot ([\text{number of layers}] \cdot w^{(4D)})$$

because

$$v^{(4D)} \cdot h^{(4D)} \cdot d^{(4D)} \cdot w^{(4D)} \neq v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \cdot (\mathbb{R}_{>0} \cdot w^{(4D)})$$

$$v^{(4D)} \cdot h^{(4D)} \cdot d^{(4D)} \cdot w^{(4D)} \neq v^{(3D)} \cdot h^{(3D)} \cdot d^{(3D)} \cdot 0$$

$$v^{(4D)} \cdot h^{(4D)} \cdot d^{(4D)} \cdot w^{(4D)} \neq 0$$

So we can say that 3D space can be part of 4D space, but 4D space is not made up of layers or sets of 3D spaces.

But now let's look at the interactions between the different spaces. If 2D space exists on its own, no other space has any effect on it, and a person living in 2D space always sees his own space as flat and understands its laws, since only the laws within his own world affect him, and he is able to recognize those laws. However, if the 2D space is located in a 3D space, certain interactions may develop with the 3D space. These interactions are based on the relationship between the spaces and result in a person living in the 2D world experiencing physical effects that are the consequences of the presence of 3D space and the laws that apply there. However, despite their effect on the 2D world, these laws can only be partially understood from within the 2D world. The limitation of this knowledge is that the behavior of 3D phenomena in other parts of the 3D world is, on the one hand, unknown and, on the other hand, unknowable; only the part of the phenomenon that is currently interacting with the 2D world can be examined. At the same time, the 2D world may be capable of triggering interactions in the 3D world. For example, if the light generated in the 2D world propagated as a wave phenomenon in the 3D world, and the effects of this wave could be perceived as light in the 2D world, an interesting phenomenon could be observed.

Let's see how the wavelength of light would change if light were generated in a 2D world with a curved surface on a single plane (such as the world shown in Fig. 6) that propagates as a wave phenomenon in the 3D world.

The figure clearly shows the interaction between 2D and 3D space. The sections of 2D space marked with values $\lambda_1 - 8$ show the changes in wavelength in the 2D world. While the wavelength of waves originating from a light source at a point in the 2D world is constant in 3D space, the following pattern can be observed in 2D space: $\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \lambda_3 < \lambda_4 < \lambda_5 < \lambda_6 < \lambda_7 < \lambda_8$

In other words, there is a continuous increase in wavelength, and therefore a red shift in the light from the light source can be observed.

Figure 7: Wavelength change at the dimension boundary

Until now, for the sake of simplicity, we have calculated with a 2D space curved on a single plane, which would have formed a cylinder of infinite or finite length. But in fact, the 2D space can be curved on two planes, in which case it forms a sphere in 3D space that still appears flat from the 2D space. In fact, the larger the radius of the 3D sphere forming the 2D space, the fewer "anomalies" can be observed in the 2D space, since the deflection of the 2D space per unit length is smaller compared to the radial vector of wave phenomena propagating in a straight line in 3D.

3.2 How can we progress in understanding the interrelation between 3D and 4D space?

First, we need to clarify the terms. As mentioned earlier, the circle of the 2D world can become a sphere in the 3D world, and in 4D, this can be represented by the term hypersphere. However, it is very difficult to imagine a 4D hypersphere. For this reason, it would be a dead end in terms of understanding how it works if we wanted to formulate precise 4D spatial concepts and operations. Instead, we should start from the assumption that in our previous model, light generated in 2D space propagates as a wave phenomenon in 3D space, which is realized as light in 2D space, and now we can take a step further. Let us assume that light generated in 3D space propagates as a wave in 4D space, and that in 3D space the wave induces a material manifestation in the form of photons. This would be consistent with the observation that light exhibits both material and wave properties. Of course, this could also explain the redshift of galaxies, confirming Einstein's original hypothesis of a finite and static (time-invariant) universe, and it could also support Hubble's claim that the redshift of galaxies is only an apparent velocity. This approach could explain the cause of redshift in a way that excludes the weak point of the expanding universe theory, namely that space expands at a speed greater than the speed of light—and, in theory, at distances so extreme that it could be n times the speed of light.

But let's look at two diagrams that help us understand how light can propagate in 4D space as a wave phenomenon, which is realized as light in 3D space. Once again, we are faced with the challenge of representing 3D space in 2D, and based on this, to imagine 4D space as well. Let's imagine that curved 3D space is like a soap bubble, with a wave phenomenon spreading "inside" it, reaching different points of the bubble. The 2D drawing thus shows a slice of our soap bubble.

- L = light source
- S = 3D space forming a hypersphere
- w = wave phenomenon propagating inside the hypersphere (4D)
- O = observer
- λ1 – 8 = wavelength elongation on the "surface" of 3D space

If an observer examines an object in 3D space that is at the opposite point of the "surface" of the 4D space hypersphere, they will experience a strong elongation of the light wavelength, a large redshift.

Figure 8: Wavelength change at the hypersphere boundary – farthest point

Now let's look at an example of observing a closer light source in 3D space.

Figure 9: Wavelength change at the hypersphere boundary – near point

The question may arise as to how we interpret Hubble's and others' observations of the increase in redshift being directly proportional to distance. Well, a linear increase in redshift can be observed if the hypersphere is not divided into zones of equal size in 4D space, but rather if the changes in λ_{Δ} values observed in 3D space are used as a basis for determining the boundaries of the zones. In this case, the increase in wavelength is taken as a reference value, and grouped by "z" values, the table below shows how the heights of the individual wave propagation zones measured in 4D space change. We used known geometric formulas for the calculation. When preparing the calculations for this study, the most distant known galaxy is **MoM-z14** [Naidu et al., 2025], with a redshift of $z_{\text{spec}} = 14,44 \pm 0,02$, and a distance (relative to the distance travelled by light) of 13.53 billion light-years. Therefore, in the calculations, we assumed that the diameter of the hypersphere is approximately equal to the distance of the most distant observed galaxy, $z=15$, for which a distance of 13.545 billion light-years can be calculated.

Since, from our point of view, we can estimate the distance of galaxies and their relative distances from each other by examining the degree of their redshift, we can also divide the surface of the hypersphere into corresponding zones. The arc length of these zones measured on the surface of the hypersphere is the same (we can measure this with redshift, so we have to compare it to this), but their height measured in 4D space is different. The number of galaxies should be proportional to the size of the surface of the zones. This requires that the distribution of galaxies be approximately uniform and that our technologies detect the total number of galaxies in each zone. So, the formula for the 4D spherical cap on which the calculations are based is:

$$A_4^{\text{cap}}(h) = 2\pi R^3 \left[\arcsin \left(\sqrt{\frac{2h}{R} - \frac{h^2}{R^2}} \right) - \sqrt{\frac{2h}{R} - \frac{h^2}{R^2}} - \left(1 - \left(\frac{2h}{R} - \frac{h^2}{R^2} \right) \right) \right]$$

The approximate properties of each zone are shown in the table below:

z value	Zone height (bly)	"Arc length", 3D (bly)	Zone surface area, 4D (bly³)	Zone ratio (%)
1	1,416	1,418	340,596	5,559 %
2	1,400	1,418	582,116	9,500 %
3	1,370	1,418	689,383	11,251 %
4	1,323	1,418	729,718	11,909 %
5	1,263	1,418	723,719	11,811 %
6	1,190	1,418	682,349	11,136 %
7	1,101	1,418	612,516	9,996 %
8	1,003	1,418	525,996	8,584 %
9	0,892	1,418	428,007	6,985 %
10	0,772	1,418	327,696	5,348 %
11	0,644	1,418	231,916	3,785 %
12	0,508	1,418	146,572	2,392 %
13	0,367	1,418	77,651	1,267 %
14	0,222	1,418	29,210	0,477 %
15	0,074	1,418	4,197	0,068 %

Table 2: Characteristics of zones at different z values

For the sake of transparency, we have rounded the figures to three decimal places, which may result in slight discrepancies. These discrepancies do not affect the order of magnitude of the figures, the trends that can be established from them, or the conclusions that can be drawn.

In practice, this means that when counting galaxies, the ratios indicated in the table should be observed. That is, for the total number of galaxies in each zone, we should find the percentage indicated in the zone ratio column. The numbers will, of course, be influenced by the fact that the density of galaxies is not constant and the structure of the universe is not homogeneous. In addition, no definitive data can be given yet, as our deep space exploration technologies are still developing, but the final numbers should be something like this, or at least they would be in a universe with a homogeneous structure.

4 Can the 2D » 3D » 4D comparison be applied?

Why can the simplification applied to a 2D circle be used to illustrate a 4D hypersphere? Perhaps this topic could have been discussed in an earlier chapter, but a study cannot consist of only a first and second chapter, even if this topic deserves to be listed earlier. The following formula can be used to calculate the surface area of any hypersphere from the circumference of a 2D circle to an n -dimensional hypersphere (or n -sphere).

n = of hypersphere dimensions (2D = 1, 3D spcirclehere = 2, etc.)
 r = radius
 $\Gamma(z)$ = gamma function, which is a generalization of the factorial function. For integers, the following holds $\Gamma(k) = (k - 1)!$

$$S_n(r) = \frac{2\pi^{(n+1)/2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{n+1}{2}\right)} r^n$$

Let's apply this to 2D, 3D, and 4D projections.

Space projection (n)	Shape	Γ	Surface / volume formula $S_n(r)$
2D ($n = 1$)	Circle	$\Gamma\left(\frac{1+1}{2}\right) = \Gamma(1) = 0! = 1$	$S_1(r) = \frac{2\pi^{(1+1)/2}}{1} r = 2\pi r$
3D ($n = 2$)	Sphere	$\Gamma\left(\frac{2+1}{2}\right) = \Gamma(1.5) = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$	$S_2(r) = \frac{2\pi^{3/2}}{\sqrt{\pi}/2} r^2 = 4\pi r^2$
4D ($n = 3$)	Hypersphere	$\Gamma\left(\frac{3+1}{2}\right) = \Gamma(2) = 1! = 1$	$S_3(r) = 2\pi^2 r^3$

Table 3: Geometric shapes and surface/volume formulas in different dimensions

This means that there is proportionality, so the circumference of a 2D circle can be used as an illustration for the surface of a 4D hypersphere.

5 What shape is our 3D world in a 4D world?

The logical question arises: what shape does our 3D space have in the 4D world? Is it a tesseract, a hypersphere, or some other unknown form that cannot be defined by our concepts? We can say that the most likely scenario is that our 3D space exists in 4D space as a curved hypersphere. This probability is supported by the measurement of distances between galaxies, and the current results obtained from counting galaxies also suggest this. If it were a tesseract (hypercube), its edges would be detectable when measuring the distances between galaxies. However, if our 3D space forms a hypersphere in 4D space, we should see a steadily decreasing number when counting galaxies.

6 An additional dimension: time

If we accept that our well-known 3D world exists as part of a 4D world, but not as a constituent element of it, and that light, which in our 3D world behaves both as a wave phenomenon and as a material property, is in fact a phenomenon that arises in a 3D world but propagates as a wave in a 4D world, then we must now also deal with time. This is because we associate many things with time, such as speed, which is the distance travelled in a unit of time. And this is true for all speeds, even the speed of light.

At the beginning of the study, we mentioned that the concept of time is also difficult to define. This may well be because we have thought of time as part of our 3D world, with many people defining our 3D world as one in which time is present as an additional dimension (3D+t), forming part of the system. To some extent, observations support this approach. However, if we accept the existence of 4D space based on the above argument, then time can no longer be defined by the formula 3D+t, but by the formula 4D+t. In this case, however, we can say that time is not part of the 3D system, but part of the 4D system that affects our 3D world. We can also say that the 3D world inherits the dimension of time from the 4D world. This effect, however, differs from what we observed with light, when 3D phenomena induced 4D effects, which in turn were perceptible as 3D phenomena. In this case, the time dimension of the 4D+t world has a unidirectional effect on the functioning of our 3D world, and therefore we have no influence on it and cannot escape its effects.

7 Dark matter, dark energy

In the current cosmological model, dark matter and dark energy are concepts introduced to balance the discrepancies between observations and theory. These hypothetical entities are meant to compensate for the shortcomings of the model: dark matter explains the dynamics of galaxies, while dark energy explains the acceleration of expansion. However, with the introduction of a 4D space, these anomalies can be interpreted naturally. If our 3D world exists as part of a larger 4D structure, then gravity, the propagation of light, and other energy phenomena could be consequences

of interactions between dimensions. In this framework, there is no need for separate “dark” components: the observed effects arise from the geometry of 4D space and the interactions between 3D and 4D. Thus, dark matter and dark energy are not independent physical entities but symptoms of the limitations of the current model, which become unnecessary within the 4D approach.

8 Interpretation of Light Speed in 3D and 4D Space

The speed of light propagating in 4D space is constant; however, in our 3D world we perceive only the projection of this wave phenomenon. Redshift indicates the apparent elongation of the wavelength, which in 3D space appears as if the speed of light increased proportionally with distance. This effect is, nevertheless, only apparent: the actual speed of light in 4D space remains unchanged. The perceived increase in speed is caused by a geometric distortion arising from the 3D–4D interaction, not by any physical acceleration of light. Direct detection of this phenomenon will become possible in the future once the appropriate measurement methodology is developed and the necessary instrumentation is established to detect the speed of light that is already redshifted.

9 Conclusion

The proposed multi-dimensional model indicates that the redshift of galaxies is not exclusively a consequence of the expansion of space, but may also arise from the hyperspherical geometry of our three-dimensional world embedded in a higher, four-dimensional space. This perspective enables a geometric interpretation of redshift without having to assume the weak points of the conventional expanding universe model (such as expansion beyond the speed of light). Furthermore, the model provides a natural framework for explaining dark matter and dark energy anomalies, which may originate from interactions between the 3D and 4D dimensions. In the future, empirical testing of the model will be possible through detailed analysis of galaxy distribution and the distance dependence of redshift, as well as through the development of measurement methodologies capable of detecting phenomena propagating in four-dimensional space.

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